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ANNOTATION:

This article deals with the performance and fatigue of the body during the learning process in physical education lessons. The article reflects the capabilities of human biological nature, which serve as an indicator of his legal capacity. Proper organization of mental work and rest is an important condition for maintaining health, performance and successful mastery of academic disciplines.

АННОТАЦИЯ:

В данной статье речь идет о работоспособности и усталости организма в процессе обучения на уроках физической культуры. В статье отражены возможности биологической природы человека, служащие показателем его дееспособности. Правильная организация умственного труда и отдыха которая является важным условием сохранения здоровья, работоспособности и успешного освоения учебных дисциплин.

ANNOTATSIYA:

Ushbu maqolada jismoniy tarbiya darslarida o'quv jarayonida tananing ishlashi va charchoqlari haqida gap boradi. Maqola insonning biologik tabiatining imkoniyatlarini aks ettiradi, bu uning huquqiy qobiliyatining ko'rsatkichi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Aqliy mehnat va dam olishni to'g'ri tashkil etish salomatlikni saqlash, ishlash va o'quv fanlarini muvaffaqiyatli o'zlashtirishning muhim shartidir.

Key words: physical culture, motivation, specific activity, systematic activity, psychophysical stress.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, мотивация, специфическая деятельность, систематическая деятельность, психофизическая нагрузка.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy tarbiya, motivatsiya, maxsus tayyorgarlik, tizimli tayyorgarlik,

Performance and fatigue during the learning process.

Performance is a person's ability to perform a specific activity within given time limits and performance parameters. On the one hand, it reflects the possibility of a person's biological nature, serves as an indicator of his legal capacity, on the other

hand, it expresses his social essence, being an indicator of the success of mastering the requirements of a specific activity. The basis of performance is made up of special knowledge, abilities, skills, and certain mental, physiological, and physical characteristics. In addition, such personality traits as intelligence, responsibility, conscientiousness, etc. are of great importance for success in activity; a set of special qualities required in a specific activity. Efficiency also depends on the level of motivation, the set goal, which is adequate to the individual's capabilities.

Proper organization of mental work and rest is an important condition for maintaining health, working capacity and successful mastery of academic disciplines.

First condition. You need to “enter” any work activity gradually, since the beginning of work coincides in time with the period of work.

Second condition. For high performance, regularity and rhythm of work are necessary. Impetuousness and forced tension do not provide stable performance. Different people have different rhythms of work. However, rhythm is not a once and for all established quality - you can “cultivate” the necessary rhythm in work. Rhythm in work can be called daily work at the same hours, with reasonable alternation of it with breaks for rest. At first, organizing rhythmic work requires a conscious effort of will. As soon as a student gets involved in work, the compulsion is removed, a habit arises, work becomes a necessity. If the order in the work, its rhythm is established correctly, the student can work a lot every day without overloading himself.

The third condition is habitual consistency and systematic activity. This condition does not determine the content that will change during the semester, but it provides for a clear recording of the time of classes, their nature, breaks for lunch, dinner, travel, active recreation, cultural events, sleep, etc. The content of work for each week is largely determined by the schedule of mandatory tasks drawn up by the dean's office. The deadlines indicated in the schedule are like milestones according to which the student can plan his work.

The fourth condition is the correct alternation of work and rest, as well as the replacement of some forms of work by others. Proper alternation of mental activity with regular and sufficient sleep is one of the determining conditions for its effective implementation. It is equally important to alternate work and rest during the school day. Rest is necessary to maintain performance in order to prevent deep development of fatigue. Under these conditions, recovery processes proceed effectively. If you

continue to work without paying attention to the feeling of great fatigue, then subsequently even a long rest will not always fully restore the previous level of performance. In addition, a change in the subject of educational and work activity also has a positive effect on it. This condition is reflected in the alternation of various subjects in the university curriculum; as a consequence, it requires alternating the nature of educational work during self-preparation of students - theoretical, practical tasks, graphic work, reading.

The fifth condition for successful work is the systematic (daily) performance of mental educational work at the same hours of the day (training), as a result of which the skill is strengthened, allowing the activity to be performed more productively and in large volume.

Fatigue. Prolonged intense mental work reduces the body's ability to continue it qualitatively, and fatigue sets in as a normal reaction of the body. Fatigue can cause a state of tiredness, which appears before the onset of fatigue and is a subjective feeling of a person. Fatigue increases with a lack of understanding of the meaning of the work being performed and dissatisfaction with its results. On the contrary, increased interest and successful completion of work reduces the feeling of fatigue. Fatigue is not always detected in the simultaneous weakening of all aspects of activity. A decrease in performance in one type of educational work may be accompanied by the preservation of its effectiveness in another type. So, for example, once you are tired of performing computational operations, you can successfully engage in reading. Such fatigue, partial in nature, is characteristic of certain types of mental work and is a reversible process. Fatigue is relieved by timely effective rest, especially associated with physical activity.

The degree of development of fatigue can be determined by some external signs. But there may also be a state of general fatigue in which, for example, neither doing mathematics, nor reading literature, nor even a simple conversation are possible - you just want to sleep uncontrollably. In such conditions, an increase in mental performance due to functional overstrain is very dangerous for the body and, as a rule, causes long-term adverse consequences.

With systematic overstrain of the nervous system, overwork occurs, which is characterized by a feeling of fatigue before starting work, lack of interest in work, apathy, increased irritability, decreased appetite, dizziness and headache.

Objective signs of overwork are: loss of body weight, nervous disorders, increased tendon reflexes, instability of heart rate and blood pressure, sweating, decreased body resistance to infections, diseases, etc.

Thus, mental activity associated with psychophysical stress places high demands on the body and, under certain unfavorable conditions, can cause serious illnesses.

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